

Social

PERCEPTION OF TEACHER INVOLVEMENT IN TEACHING AND ITS EFFECT ON SCHOLASTIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Abstract

The paper is an attempt to find the effect between perception of teacher involvement in teaching and scholastic achievement of the selected Higher Secondary students. In the present study survey method was used. The investigator adopted the survey method to study the relationship between perception of teacher involvement in teaching and scholastic achievement. Investigator selected only Higher Secondary students and 30 teachers as sample in Coimbatore district using stratified random sampling. The findings reveal that there is a mild positive relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement among the selected arts group students at Higher Secondary level.

Keywords: Teacher; Higher Secondary Students; Achievement; Perception.

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1. Introduction

The teacher plays multiple roles in the school. The role of teacher is assessed in terms of his/her attendance in the class, completion of the course and interpersonal relation in the school. Till now, hardly any indicator is developed to assess the performance of teacher on the basis of learning achievement of the student. . The teacher plays multiple roles in the school. The role of teacher is assessed in terms of his/her attendance in the class, completion of the course and interpersonal relation in the school. Till now, hardly any indicator is developed to assess the performance of teacher on the basis of learning achievement of the student. The emergence of a globalized world underscoring a framework of competition, and coupled with the pressures of an exploding knowledge base, has given birth to new challenges for schools as social institutions all over the world. New demands are placed on the school, often in addition to the existing ones, to

be equipped with current knowledge and modern methods of acquiring new knowledge. The paper is an attempt to find the effect between perception of teacher involvement in teaching and scholastic achievement of the selected Higher Secondary students.

2. Method

In the present study survey method was used. Survey refers to gather information by individual samples so as to learn about the whole thing. The investigator adopted the survey method to study perception of teacher involvement in teaching and it effects scholastic achievement among higher secondary students. For the present study the investigator selected y 6 schools in and around Coimbatore. Investigator selected 150 higher secondary students and 30 teachers in this area using simple random sampling technique.

Hypothesis: 1

There will be a difference in the level of perception of teacher involvement in teaching among school teachers.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage difference in perception of teacher in teaching among school teachers.

PERCEPTION OF TEACHER INVOLVEMENT IN TEACHEING								
Low			Moderate			High		
Q1	F	%	Q2	F	%	Q3	F	%
52	10	33.33%	56	12	40%	61	8	26.66%

Table 1 exhibits the result of perception of teacher involvement in teaching among school teachers. According to the table totally 33.33% of the school teacher belong to low level of perception of teacher involvement in teaching, 40% of the school teachers belong to moderate level of perception of teacher involvement in teaching, 26.6% of the school teachers belong to high level of perception of teacher involvement in teaching. So the hypothesis No: 1 is accepted. Thus it is inferred that there is a difference in the level of perception of teacher involvement in teaching among school teachers.

Chart 1: frequency and percentage difference in perception of teacher involvement in teaching among school teachers

Hypothesis: 2

There will be a difference in the level of scholastic achievement among higher secondary school student.

Table 2: Frequency and percentage difference in scholastic achievement among higher secondary school student.

SCHOLASTIC ACHIEVEMENT								
Low			Moderate			High		
Q1	F	%	Q2	F	%	Q3	F	%
32	42	28%	43	70	46.33%	68	38	25.33

Table 2 exhibits the result of scholastic achievement among higher secondary school student. According to the table totally 28% of the higher secondary students belong to low level of scholastic achievement, 46.33% of the higher secondary students belong to moderate level of scholastic achievement, 25.33% of the higher secondary students belong to high level of scholastic achievement. So the hypothesis No: 2 is accepted. Thus it is inferred that there is a difference in the level of scholastic achievement among higher secondary school student.

Chart 2: frequency and percentage difference in scholastic achievement among higher secondary school students

Hypothesis: 3

There will be a significant relationship between teacher involvement in teaching and scholastic achievement of the Higher Secondary students.

Table 3: Relationships between teacher involvement in teaching and scholastic achievement of the Higher Secondary students.

VARIABLES	N	'r' Value	'p' Value	Result
Perception of teacher involvement in teaching	30	0.243	0.195	N.S
Scholastic achievement	150			

The above table 3 shows the relationship between perception of teacher involvement in teaching and scholastic achievement of the Higher Secondary students. According to this table the correlation value of perception of teacher involvement in teaching and scholastic achievement is 0.243 which implies that there is a mild positive relationship between perception of teacher involvement in teaching and scholastic achievement of the Higher Secondary students.

3. Conclusion

The findings reveal that there is a mild positive relationship which is considered as not significant between perception of teacher involvement in teaching and scholastic achievement among the Higher Secondary students. Also it is found that the school teachers possess moderate a level of perception of teacher involvement in teaching. And it is found that the higher secondary school students have a moderate level of scholastic achievement.

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